

Mechanics and evolution of Hsp70

G. Žoldák¹

¹Department of Biophysics, Faculty of Science, Pavol Jozef Šafárik University, Jesenná 5, 040 01 Košice, Slovakia..

e-mail: gabriel.zoldak@upjs.sk

Protein allostery requires a communication channel for functional regulation between distal sites within a protein. In the molecular chaperone Hsp70, a two-domain enzyme, the ATP/ADP status of an N-terminal nucleotide-binding domain regulates the substrate affinity of a C-terminal substrate-binding domain. Recently available three-dimensional structures of Hsp70 in ATP/ADP states have provided deep insights into molecular pathways of allosteric signals. However, direct mechanical probing of long-range allosteric coupling between the ATP hydrolysis step and domain states is missing.

In my talk, I will focus on the single-molecule mechanics and evolution of bacterial Hsp70 [1-4]. Using laser optical tweezers, my group examined the mechanical properties of a truncated two-domain DnaK(1-552ye) in apo/ADP/ATP and peptide-bound states. We find that in the apo and ADP states, DnaK domains are mechanically stable and rigid. However, in the ATP-state, SBD*ye is mechanically destabilized as the result of interdomain docking followed by the unfolding of the α -helical lid. By observing the folding state of the SBD, we could observe the continuous ATP/ADP cycling of the enzyme in real time with a single molecule. The SBD lid closure is strictly coupled to the chemical steps of the ATP hydrolysis cycle even in the presence of peptide substrate.

In a recent paper^[4], we examined how such an opening and formation of alternative subdomain interfaces of Hsp70 is affected during their evolution. In particular, insertion and deletion events (indels) can be highly disruptive for the mechanical events since such changes introduce a collective shift in the pairing interactions at communicating interfaces. Based on a multiple sequence alignment analysis of data collected from Swiss-Prot/UniProt database, we find several indel-free regions (IFR) in Hsp70. The two largest IFRs are located in interdomain regions that participate in allosteric structural changes. We speculate that the reason why the indels have a lower likelihood of occurrence in these regions is that indel events in these regions cause dysfunction in the protein due to perturbations of the mechanical balance.

Thus, the development of functional allosteric machines requires including a concept of the balance between mechanical structural elements.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by research grants from the Slovak research and development agency (No. APVV-18-0285), the Slovak Grant Agency VEGA No 1/0024/22, EU H2020 TWINNING program GA. No. 952333 project CasProt, BioPickmol, ITMS2014+: 313011AUV6 supported by the Operational Programme Integrated Infrastructure, funded by the ERDF.

References

- [1] Bauer D., et al., Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A., 2015, **112(33)**, 10389-10394.
- [2] Mandal S.S. et al., Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A., 2017, **114(23)**, 6040-6045.
- [3] Bauer D., et al., Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A. 2018, **115(18)**, 4666-4671.
- [4] Gala M., Pristaš P., Žoldák G., Int J Mol Sci., 2022, **23(5)**, 2788.